

H2020 - Research and Innovation Action

APPLICATE

Advanced Prediction in Polar regions and beyond: Modelling, observing system design and Linkages associated with a Changing Arctic climaTE

Grant Agreement No: 727862

Deliverable No. 7.5

Dissemination materials 1

Submission of Deliverable

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research & Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 727862.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

WP7: user engagement, dissemination and training aims to increase awareness of the impact of Arctic changes on weather and climate of the Northern Hemisphere by developing relevant forms of communication to spread the project results and maximise the exposure of the science produced to end-users and the public at large.

To achieve this objective, WP7 will develop several outreach materials targeted at various specific audiences that will be disseminated by the project outreach team and by project partners in occasion of seminars, conferences and at appropriate public exhibitions.

Several dissemination materials have been developed and are available to partners to use through the internal page of the project website. These include: the project logo, the project website, social media outputs (Facebook and Twitter), a project flyer, a rollup poster and an introductory presentation of the project.

Further dissemination materials will be developed throughout the project lifetime, tailored for specific end-user groups to disseminate project results, inform policies and engage with end-users. Some foreseen materials are: a biannual newsletter, a blog in close cooperation with the Year of Polar Prediction (YOPP), a series of fact sheets, a series of policy briefs in cooperation with the EU project Blue-Action and a YouTube channel.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background and objectives

One of the objectives of WP7: user engagement, dissemination and training is to increase awareness of the impact of Arctic changes on weather and climate of the Northern Hemisphere by developing relevant forms of communication. The purpose is to increase cooperation and involvement in the project, by relevant external stakeholders, spread the project results and maximise the exposure of the science produced to end-users and the public at large.

To achieve this objective, WP7 has and will develop several dissemination materials targeted at specific audiences. These will be used by the projects dissemination team and the project partners, to increase and insure as possible the projects exposure. Further, dissemination materials will be made available and targeted to the public.

The objective of this report is to summarise the project dissemination materials available as of May 2017 and to give an outlook on the new materials planned to be developed for dissemination.

1.2. Organisation of this report

In the next section a summary of the project dissemination materials available as of May 2017 is given.

Section 3 gives a preliminary outlook of further materials planned to be developed within the project.

The available dissemination materials are shown in the Annexes.

2. DISSEMINATION MATERIALS (as of May 2017)

Several dissemination materials were developed at the beginning of the project and made available to partners to use through the internal page of the project website. In addition to the dissemination materials, also all the deliverables labelled as “Public” in the project Description of Action (DoA) are available through the European portal Community Research and Development Information Service (CORDIS) and can be used to showcase the project.

Table 1: Project dissemination materials for the public as of May 2017.

Dissemination material	Target audiences	Use
Project logo	General public, Project partners	The project logo contributes to define the project identity and is used internally within the project for all written documents (e.g., deliverable reports, meeting summaries, etc.) as well as externally on all presentations and dissemination materials.
Website	General public, Project partners, Scientific community	The project website (www.applicate.eu) is the primary source of information and reference for the project. It is designed to attract visitors interested in the Arctic and gives general as well as detailed information on the project, its structure and goals, news and events. There is an internal section, with restricted access to project partners, where the

		documentation on the project (including deliverables, agreements, protocols, etc.) is stored.
Social media	General public, Project partners, Scientific community	Social media channels for the project include Twitter and Facebook. News and events related with the project are announced on social media in addition to the website. Social media is also used to interact with other projects and the rest of the Arctic community and to engage with end-users through dissemination of project results and products.
Flyer	General public, Stakeholders	The project flyer gives an overview of the project objectives, activities and partners involved. It is designed to attract interest for the project and includes the website address and primary contacts. The flyer can and will be distributed at conferences and events.
Rollup poster	General public, Stakeholders	The project roll up poster has been designed to be used at exhibitions and events. The poster has a basic design with key information on the project and the address of the website.
Project overview presentation	Project partners, Scientific Community, Stakeholders	A 4-slide overview presentation of the project gives an introduction of the project objectives and the key benefits for society. It can be used alone or integrated by partners in their presentations at conferences. The presentation includes all the partners and the project website.

3. OUTLOOK

Further dissemination materials will be developed throughout the project lifetime, tailored to specific user groups to disseminate project results, inform policies and engage with stakeholders.

Table 2: Further dissemination materials planned to be developed within the project.

Dissemination material	Target audiences	Use
Newsletter	General public, Project partners	A biannual newsletter to be issued by the outreach team through the project website and direct communication to partners and relevant stakeholders. It will summarise the main project activities and results, reports from events, news, upcoming meetings and deadlines, and vacancies within the project.
Blog	General public, Stakeholders	Developed in close cooperation with the Year of Polar Prediction (YOPP) and hosted by the Helmholtz platform, the blog “Polar Prediction Matters” will host articles for and by stakeholders on the scientific outputs of Arctic research and how these can be used/transferred to other societal sectors beyond academia. Some contributions from scientists are also planned in the blog.
Policy briefs	Stakeholders	Developed in collaboration with the EU and the EU project Blue-Action during the latter period of the project, with a focus on business and policy stakeholders, 2 policy briefs will target policy makers

		and how the scientific results from the two projects (and Arctic research in general) can inform and support policy decisions.
Fact sheets	General public, Scientific Community, Stakeholders	A series of 3-4 self-explaining 2-page documents covering a wide range of project relevant topics in Arctic research, polar prediction and how Arctic environmental changes affect mid-latitudes. Preliminary estimation is 4-6 issues.
Webinars	General public, Scientific Community, Stakeholders	Video recordings of training webinars about APPLICATE and related topics will be made publicly available on both the APPLICATE and APECS websites.
FrostByte videos	General public, Scientific Community	Produced by participants of the Polar Prediction School 2018, these 30-seconds videos will give a quick overview of the research the students are working on.
YouTube Channel	General public, Scientific Community, Stakeholders	A collection of videos (including webinars and FrostByte videos), interviews and animations relevant to the project, the project scientific results and activities.

4. REFERENCES

APPLICATE project website: www.applycate.eu

Blue Action project website: www.blue-action.eu

Year of Polar Prediction website: www.polarprediction.net/yopp/

Blog Polar Prediction Matters is going to be hosted in: <https://blogs.helmholtz.de/>

5. ACRONYMS

CORDIS Community Research and Development Information Service

DoA Description of Action

YOPP Year of Polar Prediction

6. ANNEXES

Dissemination materials: Project logo, website (screenshot examples), Twitter (screenshot examples), Facebook (screenshot examples), flyer, rollup poster, overview presentation.

APPLICATE

www.applycate.eu

Advanced prediction in Polar regions and beyond

Latest News

ECMWF generating dataset for Year of Polar Prediction

ECMWF has begun to generate an extended two-year global dataset to support the World Meteorological Organization's Year of Polar Prediction (YOPP).

The start of production was timed to coincide with the official launch of YOPP in Geneva, Switzerland, on 15 May.

6 Jun 2017

H2020-FP7 Climate Modelling Workshop

The European Commission, EASME, is organising a climate and Earth system modelling workshop (hereinafter referred as "workshop") for exploiting synergies across four H2020 projects (APPLICATE, Blue-Action, CRESCENDO and PRIMAVERA) and incorporating research outcomes from a selected number of relevant FP7 projects around the topic: Evaluating climate and Earth system models at the process level.

19 May 2017

Open research position in Polar science at the Centre for Sea Level Change, New York University Abu Dhabi (UAE)

The CSLC is looking to hire a researcher with expertise in glacier and ice shelf modelling. The scientist will work with others in a team to characterize Antarctic glaciers and assess their instability.

16 May 2017

This project (APPLICATE) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727862. The content of the website is the sole responsibility of the Consortium and it does not represent the opinion of the European Commission, and the Commission is not responsible for any use that might be made of information contained.

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Advanced prediction in Polar regions and beyond

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ECMWF generating dataset for Year of Polar Prediction

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[Read more ...](#)

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[Read more ...](#)

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[Read more ...](#)

Year of Polar Prediction – from research to improved environmental safety

Rapid change in polar regions necessitates global response

GENEVA 15 MAY, 2017 _ A concerted international campaign to improve predictions of weather, climate and ice conditions in the Arctic and Antarctic has been launched to minimize the environmental risks and maximize the opportunities associated with rapid climate change in polar regions and to close the current gaps in polar forecasting capacity.

[Read more ...](#)

Three-year PhD grant in polar weather and climate modelling at CNRS / Centre National de Recherches Météorologiques (CNRS-CNRM)

Start date: 1 October 2017

Title: Turbulent processes in the Arctic : role of the subgrid-scale variability at the marine surface due to sea ice.

[Read more ...](#)

Open Documents

Documents that are open to the general public

Default Asc 10

D7.3 User Engagement Plan New

Tuesday, 20 June 2017 Super User Open Documents

User engagement is an essential part of APPLICATE since the project needs to establish an effective dialogue with a network of key stakeholders in order to obtain feedback to help and improve weather...

Version 1.0 Hits 8 Downloads 7 Rating ★★★★★ Comments 0

Introductory slides to the APPLICATE project widescreen

Monday, 24 April 2017 Valeriya Posmitnaya Open Documents

Introductory slides to the APPLICATE project widescreen

Version 1.0 Hits 61 Downloads 10 Rating ★★★★★ Comments 0

APPLICATE_D8.2

Friday, 03 March 2017 Valeriya Posmitnaya Open Documents

Invite coordinators of BG-09 and other BG-10 projects to become members of external Advisory Board in APPLICATE

APPLICATE_D8 7

Tuesday, 06 June 2017 Super User Open Documents

To meet the growing societal need for young scientists trained in the area of weather and climate prediction, a 10-days Polar Prediction School for early-career scientists from around the world will...

Version 1.0 Hits 27 Downloads 7 Rating ★★★★★ Comments 0

Introductory slides to the APPLICATE project

Monday, 24 April 2017 Valeriya Posmitnaya Open Documents

Introductory slides to the APPLICATE project

Version 1.0 Hits 62 Downloads 11 Rating ★★★★★ Comments 0

APPLICATE_D8 5_AW1_final

Friday, 03 March 2017 Valeriya Posmitnaya Open Documents

Report from US CLIVAR working group meeting including recommendations for adjustments to the WP3 part of the APPLICATE numerical experimentation plan

Closed Documents

Documents that are only available to members of the Applicate project

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APPLICATE_stream1 and stream2_experimentprotocol
 Friday, 07 April 2017 Valeriya Posmitnaya Closed Documents
 APPLICATE - stream1 and stream2 experiment protocol

Version 1.0 Hits 1 Downloads 1 Rating ★★★★★ Comments 0

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 Thursday, 16 March 2017 Valeriya Posmitnaya Closed Documents
 Applicate logo in EPS format

Version 1.0 Hits 3 Downloads 4 Rating ★★★★★ Comments 0

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Advanced prediction in Polar regions and beyond Applicate logo in JPG format

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 Applicate logo box EPS format

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Tweets **148**
 Following **213**
 Likes **110**
 Moments **0**

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APPLICATE-EU

@applicate_eu

APPLICATE is a Horizon2020 project developing enhanced predictive capacity for weather and climate in the Arctic and Northern Hemisphere mid-latitudes.

EU

applicate.eu

Joined February 2017

15 Photos and videos

Tweets

APPLICATE-EU @applicate_eu · Jun 20

Call for papers! Session on the new #Arctic co-organised at @arcticfrontiers with @polarprediction. Deadline: 19 Sep

The New Arctic in the Global Context - Arctic Frontiers...
 The rapid changes taking place in the Arctic due to global climate change – e.g., the retreat of sea ice, a warming surface ocean and warming air masses – af...
arcticfrontiers.com

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7 April · 🌐

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16 PARTNERS FROM NINE COUNTRIES

Advancing prediction in Polar regions and beyond

**Understanding Arctic's Connections
to Weather and Climate Across
the Northern Hemisphere**

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What is APPLICATE?

A four-year project funded by the EU's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme with a budget of € 8 million

A consortium of 16 expert organisations from 9 different countries

APPLICATE's objectives:

- Assess weather and climate prediction models using observations and provide guidance for model development
- Develop enhanced predictive capacity for weather and climate in the Arctic and beyond through improving weather and climate models
- Determine how Arctic climate change influences weather and climate in the mid-latitudes of the Northern Hemisphere through atmospheric and oceanic linkages
- Provide guidance for designing the future Arctic observing system
- Communicate knowledge generated through the project to stakeholders
- Train the early career scientists in close collaboration with the Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS)

- Establish an effective dialogue with a network of key stakeholders in order to obtain feedback to help improve modelling and forecasting
- Widely disseminate the results of the project to those who can benefit from improved Arctic observations and enhanced weather and climate predictions
- Work in cooperation with European and international scientific partners
- Provide scientific and outreach support for the Year of Polar Prediction
- Build a seamless community

Cooperation as a key to success!

Those who benefit from the work of the APPLICATE project include:

- Climate scientists and modellers
- Operational forecasting centres
- Emergency services
- Any business sector that is vulnerable to climate and weather from the Arctic to the mid-latitudes (tourism, shipping, agriculture, insurance, etc.)
- Policymakers at local, regional and national levels relying on climate and weather predictions to make well-informed decisions

We welcome stakeholder feedback!

Are you a climate scientist, modeller, weather forecaster, or a user of climate and weather services? Then you are an APPLICATE stakeholder!

The APPLICATE consortium welcomes feedback from all stakeholders from outside the project to contribute to its work to improve climate and weather forecasting in the Arctic and mid-latitudes

You can get involved by joining our blog or by providing us feedback directly at:

Dr. Luisa Cristini at the Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI)
Email: luisa.cristini@awi.de
Tel.: +49(0) 471 4831-1760

Halldór Jóhannsson at the Arctic Portal
Email: halldor@arcticportal.org
Tel: +354 461 2800

Further outreach material can be found on the project webpage

APPLICATE

www.applycate.eu

Advanced prediction in Polar regions and beyond

Studying Arctic's Connections to Weather and Climate in Europe, Asia and North America

APPLICATE's objectives:

Develop advanced predictive capacity for weather and climate in the Arctic and beyond

Determine the impact of Arctic climate change on mid-latitude weather and climate

Effective knowledge transfer to stakeholders, including training of early career scientists

PARTNERS

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Understanding Arctic's Connections to Weather and Climate Across the Northern Hemisphere

A four-year project funded by the EU 's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme with a budget of € 8 million

A consortium of 16 expert organisations from 9 different countries!

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APPLICATE

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Advanced prediction in Polar regions and beyond

Université catholique de Louvain

Barcelona Supercomputing Center
Centre for Research in Data Science

APPLICATE participating partners' countries

APPLICATE's objectives:

- Develop advanced predictive capacity for weather and climate in the Arctic and beyond
- Determine the impact of Arctic climate change on mid-latitude weather and climate
- Effective knowledge transfer to stakeholders, including training of early career scientists
- Building a seamless polar prediction community

Those who benefit from the work of the APPLICATE project include:

- Climate scientists and modellers
- Operational forecasting centres
- Emergency services
- Any business sector that is vulnerable to climate and weather from the Arctic to the mid-latitudes (tourism, shipping, agriculture, insurance, etc.)
- Policymakers at local, regional and national levels relying on climate and weather predictions to make well-informed decisions

Get involved - Provide feedback - Join our blog

www.applycate.eu

